

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/373293731>

The Ten Pillars of Neuromotricity. Theoretical–practical justification according to the BAPNE method.

Article in *Retos* · August 2023

DOI: 10.47197/retos.v50.98333

CITATIONS

46

READS

2,515

2 authors:

Francisco Javier Romero-Naranjo
University of Alicante

229 PUBLICATIONS 2,511 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Eliseo Andreu-Cabrera
University of Alicante

57 PUBLICATIONS 724 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

The Ten Pillars of Neuromotricity. Theoretical-practical justification according to the BAPNE method Los Diez Pilares de la Neuromotricidad. Justificación teórico-práctica según el método BAPNE

Francisco Javier Romero Naranjo, Eliseo Andreu Cabrera
Universidad de Alicante (España)

Abstract. In this article we justify the ten basic pillars of Neuromotricity with the aim of showing a clear difference with respect to the theoretical and practical concepts of Motor and Psychomotor skills. In the first instance, a state of the art on this subject is presented, breaking down the number of publications and representative authors in order to subsequently break down the pillars that identify neuromotor skills. The foundations of Neuromotricity are articulated through its link to: Cognitive functions 2. Executive functions. 3. Attentional network. 4. Hormonal aspects. 5. Socioemotional aspects. 6. Theoretical models of learning. 7. Multiple skills. 8. Kinesthetic aspects. Forms of learning and 10. Musical aspects. The union of all these subjects is what gives Neuromotricity a clearly differentiating value from the rest of the other disciplines.

Keywords: Neuromotricity, BAPNE, Body percussion, cognitive functions, executive functions, dual task.

Resumen. En este artículo justificamos los diez pilares básicos que fundamentan la Neuromotricidad con el objetivo de mostrar una clara diferencia frente a los conceptos teórico-prácticos procedentes de la Motricidad y Psicomotricidad. En primera instancia, se presenta un estado de la cuestión sobre dicha temática desglosando el número de publicaciones y autores representativos para posteriormente desglosar los pilares que la identifican. Los fundamentos de la Neuromotricidad se articulan a través de su vínculo a: 1. Funciones cognitivas 2. Funciones ejecutivas. 3. Red atencional. 4. Aspectos hormonales. 5. Aspectos socioemocionales. 6. Modelos teóricos de aprendizaje. 7. Habilidades múltiples. 8. Aspectos cinestésicos. 9. Formas de aprendizaje y 10. Aspectos musicales. La unión de todas estas materias es lo que aporta a la Neuromotricidad un valor claramente diferenciador del resto de las otras disciplinas.

Palabras clave: Neuromotricidad, BAPNE, Percusión corporal, funciones cognitivas, funciones ejecutivas, dual task.

Fecha recepción: 08-02-23. Fecha de aceptación: 13-07-23

Francisco Javier Romero Naranjo

bapne.central@gmail.com

Introduction

Neuromotricity is a discipline that requires a very clear foundation and protocol that differentiates it from Motricity and Psychomotricity (Andreu-Cabrera & Romero-Naranjo, 2021; Romero-Naranjo & Andreu Cabrera, 2023a, 2023b). In the 21st century, information and communication technologies take time away from movement and social interaction, causing a sedentary lifestyle (in addition to low cognitive stimulation). For this reason, physical activity becomes the solution to health problems, in all the dimensions of the term. The relationship between physical activity and brain functions is one of the most developed lines of research in recent decades. From the information analyzed (Rolland et al., 2008; Loprinzi et al., 2013), it appears that, in the motor domain, physical exercise is one of the best protectors against senile dementia, Alzheimer's disease and depression (de Oliveira et al., 2019; Wu & Huang, 2017).

Physical exercise possesses invaluable human benefits (Aguilar-Herrero et al., 2021; Martínez-Heredia et al., 2021; Maureira, 2021; Maureira et al., 2023; Pacheco et al., 2022; Padiál-Ruz et al., 2022; Palma-Marifil et al., 2021; Pérez et al., 2022; Romero-Ramos et al., 2021; Zambrano-Pintado et al., 2022) that combined with other subjects the results can be even more brilliant (Luis-de Cos et al., 2019; Mezcuca-Hidalgo et al., 2020; Villa de Gregorio et al., 2019).

In the field of Physical Activity and Sport Sciences, motricity refers to a study of the movements of human beings, their characteristics and meaning. It is also defined as the capacity of the central nervous system to produce the

contraction of a muscle. Motricity as a discipline studies human movements and their kinetic and kinematic characteristics.

Following the latest studies (De Giorgio et al., 2018), exercise increases the production of neurotrophins, a protein responsible for helping us to produce more neurons, helping to have a healthy and flexible brain. That is why, every time we want to learn something new, our brain must be modified and create new structures, as Santiago Ramón y Cajal pointed out, at the beginning of the 20th century.

State of the art

With regard to neuromotricity, there are very few scientific references and studies since it is a term of recent appearance and academic development. It is important to note that for many authors Neuromotricity is to perform any type of motor exercise and then talk about the brain; an aspect completely opposite to the essence of the term. By way of justification, there are three recent articles that present a historical evolution; as well as a proposal of practical resources that serve as a precedent for this publication, citing that the first time this term appears is in 1974 by the researcher André Lapierre (Andreu-Cabrera & Romero-Naranjo, 2021; Romero-Naranjo & Andreu Cabrera, 2023a, 2023b). Still, the bibliometrics of Arnau-Mollá (Arnau-Mollá & Romero-Naranjo, 2021, 2022) and the excellent state of the art of Di Ruso (Di Ruso & Romero-Naranjo, 2023) are extremely enlightening.

A bibliographic update was carried out in 2023 on this term, providing the following table (Table 1).

Regarding the number of the most prolific authors on this term, we provide the following table (Table 2).

Table 1.

Table of documents in academic search engines.

Neuromotricity	
WOS	15 documents
Scopus	13 documents
Jstor	12 documents
Proquest	10 documents
Dialnet	19 documents
Pubmed	0 documents

Table 2.

Table of authors with the highest academic production on neuromotricity.

Most prolific authors in Neuromotricity	
Francisco Javier Romero-Naranjo	28
Antonio Francisco Arnau-Mollá	15
Roberto Sayago-Martínez	7
Eliseo Andreu-Cabrera	4
Luisamer González de Benatuil	4

All these authors belong to the University of Alicante and research within the specific research group on Neuromotricity of the Faculty of Education.

Differences between motor skills, psychomotor skills and neuromotricity.

From a theoretical and practical point of view, there are clear differences between each of these concepts, so we will now proceed to define them.

Motricity: is the ability to control the movements of the body in a voluntary and coordinated manner involving the motor system. Activities such as walking, jumping, running, rolling, crawling, going up or down stairs, etc., clearly represent motor skills.

Psychomotricity: according to the Spanish Federation of Psychomotricity Associations, "psychomotricity is the set of cognitive, emotional, symbolic and sensory-motor interactions in the capacity to be and to express oneself in a psychosocial context". Activities such as following a path, tying shoelaces, inserting one object into another according to its geometric shape, making a circuit with specific goals, etc.

There are several definitions of neuromotricity, but Romero-Naranjo (2004) is the first author to link it to executive functions through his educational proposals in the BAPNE method (Romero-Naranjo, 2018; Andreu-Cabrera & Romero-Naranjo, 2021; Romero-Naranjo & Andreu-Cabrera, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c). Next, we proceed to show the few existing definitions.

Lapierre (1974) is the first author to use the word Neuromotricity but only as a chapter title. It is important to note that he does not provide a specific definition. All he argues is that "between psychism and the mechanics of a muscle, there is a whole neurological structure of transmission and regulation" which Lapierre himself calls the psychoneuromotor system.

From the point of view of neurorehabilitation, Herando and Useros (2007) define neuromotricity as the nervous response that goes from the cortical and subcortical nerve centers and activates the motor neurons to produce a motor response.

Regarding Martín Lobo (2015) defines it as analysis of the neurological aspects involved in the development of a movement, its programming, control and the acquisition of the models of execution of the movement.

According to Romero-Naranjo & Andreu-Cabrera

(2023a, 2023b) Neuromotricity is the educational and neurorehabilitative procedure that affects cognitive stimulation through executive functions in which the dual task and mainly language (spoken, sung, recited, etc.) thus providing a superior function to stimulation. The example of language as a task independent of the upper and lower extremity is the main element that differentiates it from motor and psychomotor skills.

Concretely, the terminological and conceptual difference of the three terms is shown in the following table (Table 3).

Table 3.

Key concepts of motor, psychomotor and neuromotricity.

Key Concepts
Motricity. It is the ability to control body movements in a voluntary and coordinated manner involving the motor system. Activities such as walking, jumping, running, rolling, crawling, going up or down stairs, etc., clearly represent motor skills.
Psychomotor. It is the set of "cognitive, emotional, symbolic and sensorimotor interactions in the capacity of being and expressing oneself in a psychosocial context".
Neuromotricity. It is the educational and neurorehabilitative procedure that affects cognitive stimulation through executive functions in which the dual task and mainly language (spoken, sung, recited, etc.) coexist, thus providing a superior function to stimulation.

With all that we have observed above, we make a hierarchy that goes from automated movements to more complex skills and possibly requiring more stimulation (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Hierarchical figure of motor, psychomotor and neuromotricity.

Pillars of Neuromotricity

Neuromotricity is conditioned by a series of factors that clearly differentiate it from motor and psychomotor skills. For this reason, the executive functions and especially the dual task with the use of language is fundamental. This is the reason why we propose the basic pillars that make it up.

Cognitive functions

Through movement, cognitive functions are the basis for working neuromotricity, since this has a protocol that differs from motor and psychomotor functions (Romero-Naranjo & Sayago-Martínez et al., 2023; Romero-Naranjo & Pujalte-Cantó & Arnau-Mollá, 2023). Cognitive functions are those that are responsible for receiving, selecting, storing and processing information from the environment around us.

With movement we can work in parallel with memory, language, praxias, gnosias, spatial orientation, visuospatial

ability, attentional network, social cognition and executive functions. It is important to emphasize that spoken, recited or sung language is of utmost importance because we can use it while performing any motor activity. Clear examples are, for example, walking while bouncing a ball and performing arithmetic operations, answering capitals of countries, saying opposites (black/white), singing a melody, etc. (Kozio et al., 2012; Sheridan & Hausdorff, 2007; Yogeve-Seligmann et al., 2008).

Within cognitive functions, praxias have a very important role in neuromotricity due to their relationship with the kinesthetic part because they are a neurological process by which cognition directs motor actions. There are several types of praxias that are classified as: facial, ideomotor, ideational and visoconstructive. When we perform motor coordination activities and use objects such as balls, pikes, hoops or clubs, praxias are always present due to the appropriate use that must be given to them as well as the use of well-coordinated sequences to provide their correct execution. Praxis are very important in body expression because they involve gestures, facial grimaces, cheeks or motor movements that are detailed below.

Ideomotor praxis

It is the ability that includes the performance of simple movements such as communicative hand gestures when gesturing and saying to someone: come, goodbye, silence, military salute, a comb, a finger wave, etc.

Ideational Praxis

It is the ability related to the use of utensils or objects with a sequence of well-coordinated actions. For example, passing a tennis ball from one hand to the other, brushing our teeth, combing our hair, tying our shoelaces, threading a needle, cutting with a knife, etc. In neuromotricity we use ideational resources linked to the double task where we start from simple movements as we observe below (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Ideational praxis with a tennis ball.

In neuromotricity, praxias can be combined with language, two fundamental cognitive functions in the BAPNE method. The exposed plate should be read where each time a stick is seen, "bread" is pronounced and when two sticks are seen, "house" is pronounced (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Performance of a BAPNE activity in which coded language is implemented with ideational praxis.

Visoconstructive Praxis

It is linked to the ability to plan and execute movements in space such as doing a puzzle, assembling an ikea piece of furniture, making a drawing, or building something from its components such as a small boat, etc.

Orofacial Praxis

It is everything that has to do with movements or gestures with different parts of the face. Activities such as frowning, squeezing the cheeks, making faces, giving a kiss, clicking the tongue, etc. All these aspects are also fundamental in body expression.

Executive Functions

Executive functions are the Swiss army knife of our prefrontal cortex. From the didactic point of view, we have in our brain a toolbox that must be used according to the activity to be performed. Many authors have contributed to expose their models, such as Diamond (2013), Furley et al., (2023), Tirapu (2008), Fuster (2000), Koechlin & Sommerfield (2007), Damasio (1996), Miyake (2000), etc. In our case, we follow Tirapu's proposal since it is in line with the type of activities of the methodology.

Through movement we can work on executive functions (processing speed, working memory, inhibition, verbal fluency, dual task, cognitive flexibility, planning, branching and decision making). The concrete link of unifying executive functions to movement using language and body percussion as completely independent tasks was created by Romero-Naranjo (2004). Executive functions are the heart of neuromotricity in which dual-tasking is the differentiating element. Dual-tasking has a unique importance, considering it as the ability to perform two completely different tasks such as eating and reviewing an exam in parallel, etc.

Neuropsychology researchers have structured three classic paradigms regarding the so-called dual task (Baddeley, 1986; Falbo et al. 2016; Fritz et al., 2015; Koch et al., 2018; Mendel et al., 2015; O'Shea et al., 2022; Ruthruff et al., 2001; Sasaki et al., 2015) called Motor/Motor;

Cognitive/Cognitive; and Cognitive/Motor. Subsequently, several authors provided a fourth model named Rhythmic/Motor (Park et al., 2014; Kim et al, 2017a, 2017b, 2020, 2022) and finally Romero-Naranjo (2023a)

provides a possible fifth paradigm named Rhythmic/Motor/Cognitive.

In summary, the five paradigms of the dual task are presented as follows (Table 4).

Table 4. Classification of the five paradigms of the Dual Task.

Dual Task Paradigms	
1	Motor/Motor. These are two tasks that possess a motor component (Amboni et al., 2012; Beurskens & Bock, 2013; Hung et al., 2013; Lee et al., 2017; Shim et al., 2016). They are classified into two major blocks: A. Balancing tasks: we observe this in the hospitality world when we see a waiter carrying a tray, several plates in his hands or a simple glass of water. B. Oculo-manual tasks: an example is walking forward while fastening the buttons of a shirt.
2	Cognitive/Cognitive. These are two activities with a cognitive component (Baddeley & Hitch, 1974; Corlu et al., 2015, Wang & Gathercole 2013). A practical example is writing the alphabet on a piece of paper while answering cognitive tasks such as the capital of Germany, the opposite of white, tell me the result of 2x9, translate the word "chair" into English, etc.
3	Cognitive/Motor. It consists of performing one task with a cognitive component and another with a motor component (Bridenbaugh & Kressig, 2015; Crockett et al., 2017; Falbo et al., 2016; Fok et al., 2011; Hawkins et al., 2018; Lin & Lin, 2016). There are many variables of activities because the literature on it is abundant. The voice has a fundamental role since the person must speak continuously according to the verbal fluency tasks that are indicated. There are many variants and here we show a few of them: a) Walking and arithmetic tasks (addition, multiplication, division...) b) Walking and working memory (remembering words from a story...) c) Walking and verbal fluency (counting backwards the days of the week). d) Walking and semantic fluency (saying words beginning with "N"). e) Walking and categorical fluency (say only fruits or musical instruments...).
4	Rhythmic/Motor. It consists of performing a rhythmic and a motor task (Park et al., 2014; Kim et al, 2017). A practical example is walking forward while playing a percussion instrument following a rhythmic pattern. The same can be executed by performing a rhythmic structure with clapping.
5	Rhythmic/Motor/Cognitive (Romero-Naranjo et al, 2023a). It consists of performing a task with a motor component linked to movement, another with a cognitive component and another with a rhythmic component. The BAPNE method provides many practical variants where the novelty lies in the fact that the subject must not only speak but also sing, recite, hum, etc. For this, the methodology not only uses the body, but it is supported by hoops of different sizes, feathers, strings, chopsticks, cones, maces and other objects. The neuromotor table (Figure 4) helps the initial activities. The activities are classified into three major groups: A. Dual-task activities walking freely in space. B. Bipedal dual-task activities with geometric figures (figure 8). C. Seated dual-task activities. Each of these activities has the task of moving the lower limbs completely independently of the upper limbs while performing verbal, rhythmic or melodic fluency tasks.

The activity protocol of the BAPNE program is based on activities in which the subject must perform motor movement activities while executing rhythmic structures with the upper limb and from the verbal point of view performs cognitive activities that the teacher can indicate (addition, subtraction, country capitals, saying opposites, translating words, repeating certain changing syllabic structures, singing a melody, etc.). The BAPNE method has a "Chart" that summarizes all the variants that can be performed (Figure 4). For example, the following sequence indicates that for each step, two claps are given, and the teacher can also ask you for the capital of Germany.

(Romero et al., 2022).

The executive functions and their link to neuromotor activities are as follows (Andreu-Cabrera & Romero-Naranjo, 2021; Bååth et al., 2016; Romero-Naranjo et al., 2023).

Processing speed

It indicates the amount of information that can be processed per unit of time or even the speed at which a series of cognitive operations can be performed, but also the time that elapses from the appearance of the stimulus to the execution of a response (Ríos et al., 2004). Processing speed can be visual (letters and numbers), auditory (language and singing) and movement. We work with the BAPNE Cognitive Plates and also with the Clap Change, by means of rhythmic and melodic oral question/answer structures, verbalizing mathematical operations and moving in different "horizontal meters" (geometric figures) in space.

Working memory

Several authors also call it working memory, which is the ability to record, encode, maintain and manipulate information during a very specific interval of time in order to maintain the sense of unity of cognitive activity. In various types of activities using varied repetitions and combining new rhythmic structures both verbally and with body percussion.

Verbal fluency

It is related to the processes that carry out the appropriate strategies for the search of information and its appropriate

Figure 4. Table of initial Neuromotricity activities of the BAPNE method.

All the detailed aspects of this type of activities are detailed in the publications of the BAPNE method, including the evaluation of the attentional network and anxiety

response in the shortest possible time. It works through the ability to improvise verbally within certain structures provided by the teacher. It is related to dual task since it is performed while moving in certain geometric figures.

Dual task

Dual-tasking is the ability to perform two completely different tasks simultaneously and paying equal attention to both of them constantly. It is about working in parallel a visual task and a visuospatial task. In BAPNE all the activities present dual task since the purpose is to make the lower limbs independent from the upper limbs with different movements and voice (spoken or sung).

Inhibition

It is the ability to inhibit or control impulsive responses, interferences or distracters while performing a task. It can be worked at motor, attentional and behavioral levels. Multiple activities related to psychomotor melodies, canon, concentric circles and reverse reaction.

Cognitive flexibility

It is the ability that allows us to make changes in what was previously planned and thus adapt to the circumstances of our environment. The teacher constantly provides indications that modify the psychomotor movement.

Planning

It is the ability to generate objectives, develop action plans to achieve them, and choose the most appropriate one based on anticipation of consequences. When indications of what to do next are received, the participant develops action plans to achieve them.

Decision making

It is the process of making a choice between several possible choices according to the needs, assessing the results and consequences of each one of them. Mainly works with Clap Change, Handball Change and when the student, within certain parameters, leads the group temporarily assuming the role of teacher.

Figure 5. Neuromotor pyramid according to the BAPNE method. (Romero-Naranjo & Andreu-Cabrera, 2023).

Branching

It is the ability to organize and perform three tasks optimally simultaneously, interleaving them and knowing where each of them is at any given moment.

Therefore, as a conclusion of this section we can observe that the level of complexity is always conditioned by the use of the double task in Neuromotricity, as shown in the following pyramid (Figure 5).

Attentional network

Attention allows us to selectively focus our interest on a certain stimulus, discarding, activating, filtering or inhibiting non-relevant information. Neuromotor activity requires a high level of attention because controlling that the movement is independent of language requires a high level of concentration. There are thirteen attentional models according to Fernandez (2014), exposed by different authors; models of attention with a very precise justification according to each researcher such as Broadbent, Norman and Shallice, Mesulam, Mirsky, Postner and Petersen, as summarized by Onandia-Hinchado (2019). The model proposed by Sohlberg and Mateer (1987, 1989) is the one that best fits the Neuromotricity activities of the BAPNE method. These authors classify attention in a hierarchical manner and graduating to greater complexity as arousal, focal, sustained, selective, alternating and divided. Following the postulates of Onandia-Hinchado (2019), Sohlberg and Mateer's clinical model of attention is explained as follows:

Arousal. It is the ability to be awake and to maintain alertness and therefore involves the ability to follow stimuli or commands.

Focal attention. It is the ability to focus attention on a given stimulus where the time of fixation dedicated to the stimulus is not valued.

Sustained attention. The ability to maintain a response consistently over a prolonged period of time.

Selective attention. The ability to select information from different variables with the aim of inhibiting attention to some stimuli while attending to others.

Alternating attention. The ability to switch the focus of attention between tasks that involve different cognitive requirements, controlling which information is processed at each moment.

Divided attention. According to Onandia-Hinchado "is the ability to attend to two things at the same time. It is the capacity to select more than one piece of information at the same time or more than one process or action scheme simultaneously. It is the process that allows the distribution of attentional resources to different tasks or requirements of the same task. It may require rapid switching between tasks or the automatic execution of some of them" (Onandia-Hinchado et al., 2019).

Regarding attention and neuromotricity studies there are more than 15 intervention studies with control and experimental group both in Spain and Italy such as the studies conducted in primary school (Arnau-Mollá & Romero-Naranjo, 2020; Cozzutti et al., 2017; Torró-Biosca et al., 2019), and Secondary (Álvarez-Morales & Romero-Naranjo, 2018; Romero-Naranjo, et al., 2022; Piqueres-Juan et al., 2019), also in Conservatories (Ros-Silla et al., 2019) and in healthy elderly people (González-Sánchez et al., 2019) among others.

Hormonal aspects

Hormones play a very important role in the chemical processes of our organism since they transmit messages between cells and organs (García-Arnés et al., 2022). The intergroup relationship always generates a hormonal bond both positively and negatively due to the interpersonal relationships that are generated (Romero-Naranjo & Romero-Naranjo, 2022). Our brain translates our emotional and affective bond into a series of hormones that provide emotional stability to the subject depending on the type of circumstance he/she is experiencing at that moment.

It is true that certain hormones have the duality of being also neurotransmitters because they are produced by the adrenal glands and poured into the bloodstream, which provides a hormonal effect; it is important to note that they are released in parallel in the nerve endings, also acting as neurotransmitters. Important neurotransmitters linked to motor activity and neuromotor activity are glutamate, which enhances communication between neuronal groups; dopamine, which is linked to reward and pleasure; acetylcholine, which is involved in learning and memory processes; serotonin which is linked to our mood and sleep processes; endorphins which have the ability to inhibit neurons involved in pain and regulate the release of stress; noradrenaline which is involved in keeping us awake, active and focused.

Socioemotional aspects

Emotions have a unique value when it comes to relating and working collaboratively. There are several models on working with emotions such as Plutchik (1980), Salovey & Mayer (1990), Bisquerra (2011), Aguado (2014a, 2014b), Ibarrola (2001), Cowen & Keltner (2017), etc. In the case of neuromotor we follow the model of Roberto Aguado (2014), in which he classifies pleasant emotions into CASA (curiosity, admiration, security and joy) and unpleasant emotions TRAM (sadness, anger, disgust and fear). Regarding the socioemotional bases from the neuromotor point of view, there is a previous publication that provides the ten pillars of socioemotional learning, which are divided into:

1. Systematic learning.
2. Learning based on cognitive and executive functions.
3. Environment. Forms of learning.
4. Non-hierarchical learning.
5. My relationship with the other.
6. Link with the error and link with the methodology.
7. Infrastructure. Classroom conditions and materials.
8. Creativity. Teacher's competence and voice.
9. The value of play.
10. Evaluation.

Theoretical models of learning

The way in which we teach and disseminate knowledge can vary depending on the optic in which we focus the information.

Gregorc's model

Our learning style depends on our way of perceiving and ordering information (Terry, 2002). Depending on the culture and personality of the student, learning can be linear (first course, second course, third course, etc.) or random

(typical of non-Western cultures).

Kolb's model

This celebrated author elaborated his well-known "Learning Style Inventory" (Manolis et al., 2013). He proposes four possible ways of learning:

- a) Concrete experience: those people who prefer to learn through the experience of active participation and their relationship with other people.
- b) Reflective observation: These are people who discover the meaning of learning through listening, observation and attending to diverse opinions.
- c) Abstract conceptualization: People who prioritize learning through abstract theories and concepts.
- d) Active experience: People who prefer to learn by testing theories and experimenting with them.

Myers Briggs Model

The Myers Briggs model is based on Carl Jung's work on psychological types (Salter et al., 2006). In pedagogy it is taken into account when looking at the psychological profiles of our students because we will understand the need to diversify with respect to what and how we ask them to learn. This model classifies four categories that describe key areas, which when combined form the basis of a person's personality. These are:

- a) The center of their attention: Extroversion (E) or Introversion (I).
- b) The way of perceiving information: Sensation (S) or Intuition (N).
- c) The way of making decisions: Thinking (T) or Feeling (F).
- d) The way of dealing with the external world: Judgment (J) or Perception (P).

Dunn & Dunn Model

Rita and Kenneth Dunn's model is the most comprehensive in providing insight into the learner's preferred way of learning, possessing a full spectrum of age, ability, and gender (Klitmøller, 2015). Dunn & Dunn's studies based the mode of learning on five categories: environmental (is structured in sound, light, temperature and design), emotional (consists of motivation, constancy, responsibility, structure), sociological (focuses on self, with another person, with peers, with adults, various), physiological (is visual, auditory, kinesthetic and tactile) and psychological (articulated in global, analytical, left or right hemisphere dominance, impulsive or reflective).

Multiple skills

Through neuromotoricity we can work multiple skills where the kinesthetic part and praxis have a relevant role. Cognitive functions serve as a link to justify many skills. For this reason, there is a link between cognitive functions and multiple skills. Language with linguistic ability; praxis with kinesthetic ability; social cognition with interpersonal and intrapersonal skills, and the same happens with visuospatial

ability, etc. For this reason, we believe that students may feel more comfortable working within some parameters than others.

Kinesthetic aspects

Neuromotor skills revolve around movement and for this reason biomechanics, body schema and expression serve as a bridge for the development of activities. In this regard, there is already initial literature on biomechanics (Alonso-Marco & Romero-Naranjo, 2022), laterality (Romero-Naranjo, 2013a, 2013b, 2013c; 2014, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020a, 2020b, 2020c, 2020d, 2020e), fine psychomotor skills (Carretero-Martínez, 2016), body schema (Romero-Naranjo et al., 2022), etc. The activities require specific motor skills that are sequenced and aim to provide "motor literacy" in a correct way.

A basic neuromotor activity is the Clap Change, which aims to dissociate the lower train from the upper train through "micro-activities" that vary. The student counts from one to four whose numbers coincide with the movement of the feet. The teacher will tell him/her on which number to clap his/her hands, since they are continuously changing (Figure 6). Subsequently, many variants can be performed, such as the mathematical one, where the students are told to clap on 2+1 or 3 - 1, etc. Another variant is to sing a melody while it is being played and to pay attention to the numerical indications given by the teacher. There are more than 20 variants of this activity based on the double task.

Figure 6. Geometric figure model to work on Clap Change.

Figure 7. Sample of some visuospatial learning models.

Visuospatial forms of learning

From the point of view of the execution of movement in space, neuromotor skills, having a specific protocol, the activities can be carried out in different ways. The visuospatial ability can be worked in different ways such as working in pairs, circles, concentric circles, facing rows, quartets or sextets, among other possibilities (Figure 7).

Musical aspects

In neuromotor skills, many of the exercises require a temporal structure of movement called rhythm (Romero-Naranjo, 2020e). One of the first activities is the proposal of movement by geometric figures, which allows students to know when each rhythmic structure or beat begins and ends (Figure 8). Through multiple neuromotor activities we can work on pulse, rhythm, meter, musical figures, metrical division and subdivision, beats and counter beats, timbre, aglogic, improvisation and even some basic rudiments of composition, as well as other structures such as

Figure 8. Geometric movement of the feet in neuromotor skills. canon, echo, etc.(Romero-Naranjo et al 2022a, 2022b, 2022c).

Figure 8. Geometric movement of the feet in neuromotor skills.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we would like to emphasize that we have proposed the 10 fundamental pillars that justify the use of neuromotor skills. To this end, we have provided not only the theoretical and bibliographical justification that supports it, but also various practical resources that show that neuromotor skills have clear differences with the classic activities from psychomotor skills (Table 5).

Table 5.
Benefits and contents of the BAPNE method

Benefits and contents attached to Neuromotricity - BAPNE method I			
Kinesthetic / Anatomical	Psychological	Neurological / Cognitive	Etnomusicologic
Body Scheme:	Emotions CASA	Cognitive functions work:	Learning of work songs and their relationship with movement and body percussion.
Postural Control / Attitude	Emotions TRAM (Roberto Aguado)	Memory	Knowledge of chroniclers, travelers and explorers.
Spatial Structuring	Rooting: gaze, hands, feet (Lowen).	Language	Introduction to the learning of the TALA of India.
Temporal Structuring	Increased motivation	Praxis	Learning of the dances percussed by geographical zones: Verbunk
Balance	Improvement of self-concept	Gnosias	Schuhplattler
Coordination	Improvement of self-esteem	Spatial orientation	Esku dantza
Learning by biomechanical planes	Acceptance of error as a vital learning process	Visuospatial ability	Haka
Learning by biomechanical axes	Bonding work	Attentional network	Gumboot
Manual and pedal coordination (audio/visual/motor)	Frustration management	Social cognition	Kecak
Motor dissociation	Management of socioemotional aspects	Executive functions	Stepping
Development of the proprioceptive system	Stimulation of play in learning	Executive functions work:	Balls dels Moretons
Development of the vestibular system	Sense of belonging to the group (tribe)	Processing speed	Flamenco, etc.
Strength work	Learning theories and models	Working memory	Types of clapping by geographical zones:
Resistance work	Forms of learning in BAPNE:	Inhibition	Gnawa
Power work	Imitation	Verbal fluency	Somali
Work on laterality	Reverse reaction	Dual Task	Deaf
Knowledge of joints and bone structures in relation to neuromotor skills.	Variable Circular Coordination	Cognitive flexibility	Bright
Learning of different types of timbres and sounds with the body.	Real-time signalin	Planning	Cameroon, etc.
Learning of clapping games and their modification to bring them to the classroom.	Learning in values	Branching	Learning urban rhythms
Movement technique / Motor coordination technique.	Evolutionary stages of neuromotor learning.	Decision Making	Learning African rhythms
BAPNE FIT program.		Frontal lobe	Learning Latin rhythms
BAPNE BODY EXPRESSION Program.		Parietal lobe	Learning Asian and Oceanian rhythms
		Temporal lobe	
		Occipital lobe	
		Hormones in Neuromotricity (Serotonin, Cortisol, Oxytocin...)	
		Possible stimulation of the cerebellum	
		Amygdala	
		Motor learning	
		Motor control	
		Motor programming	
		BDNF	
		Attentional network (Sohlberg and Matter, 1989).	
		Work of the various types of memory (procedural, etc).	

It is true that many researchers have lent themselves to terminological confusion by linking neuromotor skills to any type of movement, but simply adding a justification of the possible areas involved in its execution. Neuromotricity is a completely independent discipline that since the BAPNE method was first linked to executive functions. In the first instance, the voice, as we have argued above, is a differentiating element with a broad neurological justification in terms of cognitive stimulation. Since 1974, when the term neuromotor skills was first announced at the academic level by Lapierre, little has been written about this new field in a serious way. Proof of this is the bibliographic review of this terminology in academic search engines, which shows few studies with control and experimental groups (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Web of Science publications of the BAPNE method.

In the same way we can have an overview of the publications in the Web of Science of the classical methodologies (Figures 10,11,12,13 and14).

Figure 10. Web of Science publications about Orff.

Figure 11. Web of Science publications about Kodaly.

Figure 12. Web of Science publications about Dalcroze.

Figure 13. Web of Science publications about Suzuki.

Figure 14. Web of Science publications about Willems.

Regarding the BAPNE method, future perspectives should be linked to new intervention studies with validated tests and where motor aspects are combined with executive functions to observe if there is not only a motor improvement but also an improvement in inhibition, cognitive flexibility, working memory, planning, decision making, etc.

References

- Aguado-Romo, R. (2014). *Es emocionante saber emocionarse*. Madrid: EOS. ^[1]_[5EP]
- Aguado-Romo, R. (2014). La emoción decide y la razón justifica. *Padres y Maestros / Journal of Parents and Teachers*, (357), 15-19.
- Aguilar-Herrero, M., García Fernández, C. M., & Gil del Pino, C. (2021). Efectividad de un programa educativo en Educación Física para fomentar las habilidades socioafectivas y prevenir la violencia en educación primaria [Effectiveness of educational program in physical education to promote socio-Affective skills and prevent]. *Retos*, 41, 492-501. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v0i41.82683>
- Alonso-Marco, M., & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2022). Introducción al análisis cinemático de los movimientos básicos de la percusión corporal según el Método BAPNE [Introduction to kinematic analysis of basic body percussion movements according to the BAPNE Method]. *Retos*, 46, 950-971. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v46.94773>
- Alonso-Sanz, A., & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2015). El círculo en la relación espacio y cuerpo. Foto-Ensayo a partir de Isidro Blasco y el método BAPNE [The circle in the relationship between space and body. Photo-Essay based on Isidro Blasco and the BAPNE method]. *Arte, Individuo y Sociedad*, 27(3), 359-374. https://doi.org/10.5209/rev_ARIS.2015.v27.n3.41382
- Álvarez-Morales, L. J., & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2019). Pilot study into executive functions with muslim and christian pupils in the city of Ceuta using body percussion. *The European Proceedings of Social & Behavioural Sciences EpSBS*, 60, Article 92. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2019.04.02.92>
- Amboni, M., Barone, P., Iuppriello, L., Lista, I., Tranfaglia, R., Fasano, A., Picillo, M., Vitale, C., Santangelo, G., Agosti, V., Iavarone, A., & Sorrentino, G. (2012). Gait patterns in parkinsonian patients with or without mild cognitive impairment. *Movement Disorders*, 27(12), 1536-1543. [10.1002/mds.25165](https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.25165)
- Andreu-Cabrera, E., & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2021). Neuromotricidad, psicomotricidad y motricidad. Nuevas aproximaciones metodológicas [Neuromotricity, psychomotricity and motor skills. New methodological approaches]. *Retos*, 42, 924-938. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v42i0.89992>
- Arnau-Mollá, A. F., & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2020). Quantitative study on selective attention in children aged 8-9 years through bodypercussion. *European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 84(6), 50-60. <https://doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2020.05.6>
- Arnau-Mollá, A. F., & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2022a). A bibliometric study on body percussion based on high impact search engines. *Retos*, 45, 679-692. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v45i0.92653>
- Arnau-Mollá, A. F., & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2022b). Body percussion as a pedagogical resource. Bibliometric study on body percussion based exclusively on secondary search engines. *Retos*, 46, 809-825. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v46.95178>
- Arnau-Mollá, A. F. & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2022). Body percussion research as an object of study based on neuromotricity and executive functions: Research design. In M. d. M. Molero Jurado, A. B. Barragán Martín, M. d. M. Simón Márquez, & Á. Martos Martínez (Comps.), *Innovación Docente e Investigación en Educación: Experiencias de Cambio en la Metodología Docente* (pp. 775-785). Dykinson, S.L.
- Arnau-Mollá, A. F. & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2022). Evolution of the bapne method as an innovation method based on its justification in scientific-academic publications. In M. d. M. Molero Jurado, A. B. Barragán Martín, M. d. M. Simón Márquez, & Á. Martos Martínez (Comps.), *Innovación Docente e Investigación en Educación: Experiencias de Cambio en la Metodología Docente* (pp. 485-496). Dykinson, S.L.
- Arnau-Mollá, A. F. & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2022). Urban rhythms and creativity: Proposals for didactic innovation from neuromotricity through the BAPNE method. In Á. Martos Martínez, A. B. Barragán Martín, M. d. C. Pérez Fuentes, M. d. M. Molero Jurado, M.

- d. M. Simón Márquez & M. Sisto (Comps.), *Acercamiento Multidisciplinar Para la Investigación e Intervención en Contextos Educativos* (pp. 463-474). Dykinson, S.L.
- Asurmendi Telleria, E. & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2022). How to teach body percussion through neuromotricity in the BAPNE method. In M. d. M. Molero Jurado, A. B. Barragán Martín, M. d. M. Simón Márquez, & Á. Martos Martínez (Comps.), *Innovación Docente e Investigación en Educación: Experiencias de Cambio en la Metodología Docente* (pp. 767-774). Dykinson, S.L.
- Bååth, R., Tjøstheim, T. A., & Lingonblad, M. (2016). The role of executive control in rhythmic timing at different tempi. *Psychonomic bulletin & review*, 23, 1954-1960.
- Baddeley, A. D., & Hitch, G. (1974). Working Memory. *Psychology of Learning and Motivation*, 8, 47-89. 10.1016/S0079-7421(08)60452-1
- Beurskens, R., & Bock, O. (2013). Does the walking task matter? Influence of different walking conditions on dual-task performances in young and older persons. *Human Movement Science*, 32(6), 1456-1466. 10.1016/j.humov.2013.07.013
- Bisquerra Alzina, R. (2011). Educación emocional. *Padres y maestros*.
- Carretero-Martínez, A., Romero-Naranjo, F. J., Pons-Terres, J. M., & Crespo-Colomino, N. (2014). Cognitive, visual- Spatial and psychomotor development in students of Primary Education through the body percussion - BAPNE method. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 152 (October 7, 2014), 1282-1287. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.09.363>
- Castelló-Juan, B., Antón-Suay, M. T., Flores-Morales, N., Vicedo-Reche, M., & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2019). Evaluating executive functions in primary school children in Alicante using body percussion. The European Proceedings of Social & Behavioural Sciences EpSBS, 60, Article 70. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2019.04.02.70>
- Corlu, M., Muller, C., Desmet, F., & Leman, M. (2015). The consequences of additional cognitive load on performing musicians. *Psychology of Music*, 43(4), 495-510. 10.1177/0305735613519841
- Cozzutti, G., Guaran, F., Blessano, E., & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2017). Effects on executive functions in the BAPNE method; A study on 8-9 years old children in Friuli Venezia Giulia, Italy. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 237(February 21, 2017), 900-907. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2017.02.126>
- Cowen, A. S., & Keltner, D. (2017). Self-report captures 27 distinct categories of emotion bridged by continuous gradients. *Proceedings of the national academy of sciences*, 114(38), E7900-E7909.
- Damasio, A. R. (1996). The somatic marker hypothesis and the possible functions of the prefrontal cortex. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B: Biological Sciences*, 351(1346), 1413-1420.
- De Giorgio, A., Kuvačić, G., Milić, M., & Padulo, J. (2018). The brain and movement: How physical activity affects the brain. *Montenegrin journal of sports science and medicine*, 7(2), 63-68.
- de Oliveira, L. D. S. S. C. B., Souza, E. C., Rodrigues, R. A. S., Fett, C. A., & Piva, A. B. (2019). The effects of physical activity on anxiety, depression, and quality of life in elderly people living in the community. *Trends in psychiatry and psychotherapy*, 41, 36-42.
- Diamond, A. (2013). Executive functions. *Annual review of psychology*, 64, 135-168.
- Di Russo, S., & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2021a). *Body Percussion in Spanish Music: A Methodological Approximation* [Article]. ERPA 2021 International Congresses on Education, Sakarya, Turkiye.
- Di Russo, S., & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2021b). *Body Percussion In The Work Of Composer Oscar Navarro. *The Case Of "Libertadores* [Article]. ERPA 2021 International Congresses on Education, Sakarya, Turkiye.
- Di Russo, S., & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2023). Percusión corporal y danzas tradicionales. El caso de Ball dels Moretons en Mallorca (Body percussion and traditional dances. The case of Ball dels Moretons in Mallorca). *Retos*, 49, 442-458. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v49.97609>
- Falbo, S., Condello, G., Capranica, L., Forte, R., & Pesce, C. (2016). Effects of physical-cognitive dual task training on executive function and gait performance in older adults: a randomized controlled trial. *BioMed research international*.
- Federación de Asociaciones de Psicomotricistas del Estado Español (FAPEe)
- Fernández, A. L. (2014). Neuropsicología de la atención. Conceptos, alteraciones y evaluación [Neuropsychology of attention. Concepts, alterations and evaluation]. *Revista Argentina de Neuropsicología*, 25, 1-28.
- Fritz, N. E., Cheek, F. M., & Nichols-Larsen, D. S. (2015). Motor-Cognitive dual-Task training in neurologic disorders: A systematic review. *Journal of Neurologic Physical Therapy: JNPT*, 39(3), 142.
- Furley, P., Schütz, L. M., & Wood, G. (2023). A critical review of research on executive functions in sport and exercise. *International Review of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 1-29.
- Fuster, J. M. (2000). Executive frontal functions. *Experimental brain research*, 133, 66-70.
- García-Arnés, J. A., & García-Casares, N. (2022). Endocrinología del dopaje y los deportes: andrógenos anabolizantes. *Revista Clínica Española*.
- González de Benatuil, M. L. M., Liendo Cárdenas, A., Asurmendi Telleria, E. & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2022). Bruno Mars and body percussion: Creative strategies from neuromotricity with the BAPNE method. In Á. Martos Martínez, A. B. Barragán Martín, M. d. C. Pérez Fuentes, M. d. M. Molero Jurado, M. d. M. Simón Márquez & M. Sisto (Comps.), *Acercamiento Multidisciplinar Para la Investigación e Intervención en Contextos Educativos* (pp. 449-461). Dykinson, S.L.

- González Sánchez, O. S., Romeu López, C. E., & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2019). Pilot study of executive functions in elderly adults in care homes. *The European Proceedings of Social & Behavioural Sciences EpSBS*, 60, Article 95. <https://doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2019.04.02.95>
- González-Sánchez, O.S., Romeu-López, C.E., Sayago-Martínez, R. & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2021). *Body percussion and the cuban clave in the BAPNE Method* [Article]. ERPA 2021 International Congresses on Education, Sakarya, Turkiye.
- Hernando, A. y Useros, A. (2007). Intervención fisioterápica en el proceso rehabilitador de pacientes con daño cerebral adquirido. *Acción psicológica*, 4 (3), 35-48.
- Hung, Y., Meredith, G. S., & Gill, S. V. (2013). Influence of dual task constraints during walking for children. *Gait & Posture*, 38(3), 450-454. [10.1016/j.gaitpost.2013.01.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2013.01.009)
- Ibarrola, B. (2001). La educación emocional. *Infancia: educar de 0 a 6 años: revista de la Associació de Mestres Rosa Sensat*.
- Kim, S. J., Cho, S.-R., & Yoo, G. E. (2017a). Age-Related Changes in Bimanual Instrument Playing with Rhythmic Cueing. *Front. Psychol.* 8, (Article 1569). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01569>
- Kim, S. J., Cho, S. R., & Yoo, G. E. (2017b). The applicability of rhythm-motor tasks to a new dual task paradigm for older adults. *Front. Neurol.*, 8, (Article 671). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fneur.2017.00671>
- Kim, S. J., & Yoo, G. E. (2020). Rhythm-Motor Dual Task Intervention for Fall Prevention in Healthy Older Adults. *Frontiers in psychology*, 10, (Article 3027). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.03027>
- Kim, S. J., Park, J. K., & Yeo, M. S. (2022). Dual-Task-Based Music Therapy to Improve Executive Functioning of Elderly Patients with Early Stage Alzheimer's Disease: A Multiple Case Study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(19), 4-12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph191911940>
- Klitmøller, J. (2015). Review of the methods and findings in the Dunn and Dunn learning styles model research on perceptual preferences. *Nordic Psychology*, 67(1), 2-26.
- Koehlin, E., & Summerfield, C. (2007). An information theoretical approach to prefrontal executive function. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 11(6), 229-235.
- Koch, I., Poljac, E., Müller, H., & Kiesel, A. (2018). Cognitive structure, flexibility, and plasticity in human multitasking—An integrative review of dual-Task and task-Switching research. *Psychological Bulletin*, 144(6), 557.
- Koziol, L. F., Budding, D. E., & Chidekel, D. (2012). From movement to thought: executive function, embodied cognition, and the cerebellum. *The Cerebellum*, 11(2), 505-525.
- Lapierre, A. (1974). *La reeducación física* (Tomo I, II, III). Científico-Médica.
- Lee, Y., Lee, J., Shin, S., & Lee, S. (2017). The effect of dual motor task training while sitting on trunk control ability and balance of patients with chronic stroke. *Journal of Physical Therapy Science*, 24(4), 345-349. <https://doi.org/10.1589/jpts.24.345>
- Loprinzi, P. D., Herod, S. M., Cardinal, B. J., & Noakes, T. D. (2013). Physical activity and the brain: a review of this dynamic, bi-directional relationship. *Brain Research*, 1539, 95-104.
- Luis-de Cos, G., Arribas-Galarraga, S., Luis-de Cos, I., & Arruza Gabilondo, J. A. (2019). Competencia motriz, compromiso y ansiedad de las chicas en educación física [Motor competence, commitment, and anxiety in girls during physical education clases]. *Retos*, 36, 231-238. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v36i36.64243>
- Manolis, C., Burns, D. J., Assudani, R., & Chinta, R. (2013). Assessing experiential learning styles: A methodological reconstruction and validation of the Kolb Learning Style Inventory. *Learning and individual differences*, 23, 44-52.
- Martín-Lobo, P. et al. (2015). Procesos y programas de neuropsicología educativa. Catálogo de publicaciones del Ministerio: mecd.gob.es Catálogo general de publicaciones oficiales: publicacionesoficiales.boe.es Ministerio de educación, cultura y deporte. Secretaría de Estado de Educación, Formación Profesional y Universidades. Centro Nacional de Innovación e Investigación Educativa (CNIIE).
- Martín-Lobo, P. et al. (2015). Procesos e instrumentos de evaluación neuropsicológica -educativa. Catálogo de publicaciones del Ministerio: mecd.gob.es Catálogo general de publicaciones oficiales: publicacionesoficiales.boe.es Ministerio de educación, cultura y deporte. Secretaría de Estado de Educación, Formación Profesional y Universidades. Centro Nacional de Innovación e Investigación Educativa (CNIIE).
- Martínez Heredia, N., Santaella Rodríguez, E., & Rodríguez-García, A.-M. (2021). Beneficios de la actividad física para la promoción de un envejecimiento activo en personas mayores. Revisión bibliográfica [Benefits of physical activity for the promotion of active aging in elderly. Bibliographic review]. *Retos*, 39, 829-834. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v0i39.74537>
- Mendel, T., Barbosa, W. O., & Sasaki, A. C. (2015). Dual task training as a therapeutic strategy in neurologic physical therapy: a literature review. *CEP*, 41810, 480.
- Maureira Cid, F., Flores Ferro, E., Hadweh Briceño, M. ., Paredes Araya, D., & Morales Lillo, M. (2023). Efectos de diversos intervalos de tiempo e intensidades de ejercicio aeróbico sobre los niveles de atención selectiva y sostenida en estudiantes universitarios (Effects of varying intervals of time and intensities of aerobic exercise on levels of selective and sustained attention in university students). *Retos*, 47, 915-919. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v47.96926>
- Maureira Cid, F. (2021). Efectos de una sesión de ejercicio aeróbico sobre las correlaciones no lineales del cerebro

- en reposo (Effects of an aerobic exercise session on non-linear correlations of resting brain). *Retos*, 39, 585–591. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v0i39.81363>
- Mollinedo Cardalda, I., Pereira Pedro, K. P., López Rodríguez, A., & Cancela Carral, J. M. (2021). Aplicación de un programa de ejercicio físico coordinativo a través del sistema MOTomed® en personas mayores diagnosticadas de Enfermedad de Parkinson moderado-severo. Estudio de casos (Application of a physical exercise coordinating program by MOTomed®). *Retos*, 39, 13–17. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v0i39.78385>
- Mezcua-Hidalgo, A., Ruiz-Ariza, A., Ferreira Brandão de Loureiro, V. A., & Martínez-López, E. J. (2020). Capacidades físicas y su relación con la memoria, cálculo matemático, razonamiento lingüístico y creatividad en adolescentes (Physical capacities and their relation with memory, mathematical calculation, linguistic reasoning, and creativity in adolescents). *Retos*, 37, 473–479. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v37i37.71089>
- Miyake, A., Friedman, N. P., Emerson, M. J., Witzki, A. H., Howerter, A., & Wager, T. D. (2000). The unity and diversity of executive functions and their contributions to complex “frontal lobe” tasks: A latent variable analysis. *Cognitive psychology*, 41(1), 49-100.
- Onandia-Hinchado, I., Sánchez-Sansegundo, M., Oltra-Cucarella, J. (2019). *Evaluación neuropsicológica de los procesos atencionales*. Editorial Síntesis.
- O’Shea, S., Morris, M. E., & Iansek, R. (2002). Dual task interference during gait in people with Parkinson disease: effects of motor versus cognitive secondary tasks. *Physical therapy*, 82(9), 888-897.
- Pacheco, E., Villafuerte-Holguín, J., & López, J. (2022). Actividad física y motivación al aprendizaje del inglés como lengua extranjera en niños pequeños de Ecuador [Physical activity and motivation for learning English as a foreign language in young children in Ecuador]. *Retos*, 44, 988-998. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v44i0.90137>
- Padial-Ruz, R., García-Molina, R., González Valero, G., & Ubago-Jiménez, J. (2022). Actividad física y movimiento integrados en la enseñanza de una segunda lengua desde una edad temprana: Una revisión sistemática [Physical activity and movement integrated into the second language teaching from an early age: A systematic review]. *Retos*, 44, 876-888. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v44i0.91506>
- Palma-Marifil, T., Carroza-Sepulveda, D., Torres-Lorca, R., Pobleto-Aro, C., Cadagan, C., & Castillo-Paredes, A. (2021). Cambios en los síntomas de inatención, hiperactividad e impulsividad en niños y adolescentes con TDAH mediante los Deportes. Una revisión [Changes in symptoms of inattention, hyperactivity and impulsivity in children and adolescents with ADHD through Sports. A review]. *Retos*, 41, 701-707. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v41i0.78201>
- Park, B., & Brünken, R. (2014). The rhythm method: A new method for measuring cognitive load—An experimental dual Task study. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, 29(2), 232-243. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.3100>
- Park, J. K., & Kim, S. J. (2021). Dual-Task-Based drum playing with rhythmic cueing on motor and attention control in patients with parkinson’s disease: A preliminary randomized study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(19), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph181910095>
- Pashler, H. (1994). Dual-Task interference in simple tasks: Data and theory. *Psychological Bulletin*, 116(2), 220.
- Pérez Hernández, H., Simoni Rosas, C., Fuentes-Rubio, M., & Castillo-Paredes, A. (2022). La ludomotricidad y habilidades motrices básicas locomotrices (Caminar, correr y saltar). Una propuesta didáctica para la clase de educación física en México [Ludomotricity and basic locomotion motor skills (Walk, running and jump). A didactic proposal for the physical education class in Mexico]. *Retos*, 44, 1141-1146. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v44i0.91338>
- Piqueres-Juan, I., Sarmiento-Alienes, S., Sánchez-González, E., & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2019). Pilot study into sustained and selective attention using the BAPNE method. *The European Proceedings of Social & Behavioural Sciences*, 60(93), 751-759. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2019.04.02.93>
- Plutchik, R. (1980). A general psychoevolutionary theory of emotion. In *Theories of emotion* (pp. 3-33). Academic press.
- Ríos, M., Periañez, J. A., & Muñoz-Céspedes, J. M. (2004). Attentional control and slowness of information processing after severe traumatic brain injury. *Brain injury*, 18(3), 257-272.
- Rolland, Y., van Kan, G. A., & Vellas, B. (2008). Physical activity and Alzheimer’s disease: from prevention to therapeutic perspectives. *Journal of the American Medical Directors Association*, 9(6), 390-405.
- Romero Naranjo, F. J. (2004). Body music body percussion: propuestas didácticas sobre psicomotricidad rítmica. *Música y educación: revista internacional de pedagogía musical*.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2008). Percusión corporal en diferentes culturas [Body percussion in different cultures]. *Música y Educación: Revista Trimestral de Pedagogía Musical*, 21(76), 46- 97.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2012). Percusión corporal y lateralidad. Método BAPNE [Body percussion and laterality. BAPNE Method]. *Música y Educación: Revista Trimestral de Pedagogía Musical*, 25(91), 30-51.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2013a). Criterios de evaluación en la didáctica de la percusión corporal - Método BAPNE [Evaluation criteria in the didactics of body percussion - BAPNE Method]. *Educatio Siglo Xxi*, 31(1), 235-253.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2013c). Percusión corporal en Indonesia y Sudáfrica: Recursos para el aula [Body Percussion in Indonesia and South Africa: Resources for

- the Classroom]. *Música y Educación: Revista Trimestral de Pedagogía Musical*, 26(93), 38-47.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2013b). Science & Art of body percussion: A review. *Journal of Human Sport & Exercise*, 8(2), 442-457. <https://doi.org/10.4100/jhse.2012.82.11>
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2014). *BAPNE method: Body percussion and multiple intelligences. Cognitive, social-Emotional and psychomotor stimulation* (10th ed., Vols. 1-5). Body Music Body Percussion Press.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2016). Europa y América. Música litúrgica en ámbito hispánico. La catedral de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria y su maestro de capilla Diego Durón de Ortega (* 1653;† 1731) Documentación y marcas de agua. *Anuario Musical*, (71), 57-80.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2017). *Bodypercussion - Programación didáctica* (4th ed. Vols. 1&2) Body Music Body Percussion Press.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2018). *Bodypercussion basic*. Body Music Body Percussion Press.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2019). *Handball change* (4th ed., Vols. 1-5). Body Music Body Percussion Press.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2020a). *BAPNE Fit 1*. Body music Body percussion Press.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2020b). *BAPNE Fit 2*. Body music Body percussion Press.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2020c). Body Percussion in the Physical Education and Sports Sciences. An Approach to its systematization according to the BAPNE Method. *International Journal of Innovation and Research in Educational Sciences*, 7(5), 421-431.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2020d). La percusión corporal como recurso interdisciplinar [Body percussion as an interdisciplinary resource]. In A. J. Calvino (Coord.), *Informe especial Odite sobre tendencias educativas: Educación en tiempos de pandemia* (nº 3, época 2, pp. 134-143). Procompal publicaciones.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2020e). Percusión corporal y "Solfeo cognitivo". Recursos pedagógicos según el método BAPNE [Body percussion and "Cognitive solfeggio". Pedagogical resources according to the BAPNE method]. *Pensamiento Actual*, 20(35), 105-121. <https://doi.org/10.15517/PA.V20I35.44398>
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J., & Sayago-Martínez, R. (2021a). *Music motor control and dual task. Handball change as a musical-Motor paradigm* [Written submission]. ERPA 2021 International Congresses on Education, Sakarya, Turkiye.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J., & Sayago-Martínez, R. (2021b). *Rhythm, cognitive solfege and body percussion. Proposal for educational* [Written submission]. ERPA 2021 International Congresses on Education, Sakarya, Turkiye.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J., Andreu-Cabrera, E., & Arnau-Mollá, A. F. (2022a). Neuromotricidad y esquema corporal. Bases para el uso de la percusión corporal en las ciencias de la educación física y el deporte [Neuromotricity and body schema. Bases for the use of body percussion in the sciences of physical education and sport]. *Retos*, 47, 615-627. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v47.95922>
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J., & Romero-Naranjo, A. A. (2022). Percusión corporal y salud. Una breve aproximación al estado de la cuestión [Body percussion and health. A brief approach to the state of the art]. *Eufonía*, 93, 16-23.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J., Arnau-Mollá, A. F., González de Benatuil, M. L. M., Liendo Cárdenas, A., Di Russo, S., Salerno, G., Asurmendi Telleria, E. & Sempere García, C. (2022b). Neuromotricity and mathematics in children: Methodological approach based on rhythmic-Motor activities. In M. d. M. Molero Jurado, A. B. Barragán Martín, M. d. M. Simón Márquez, & Á. Martos Martínez (Comps.), *Innovación Docente e Investigación en Educación: Experiencias de Cambio en la Metodología Docente* (pp. 745-755). Dykinson, S.L.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J., Arnau-Mollá, A. F., González de Benatuil, M. L. M., Salerno, G., Liendo Cárdenas, A., Asurmendi Telleria, E. & Di Russo, S. (2022c). Chocolate: Body percussion and creativity from the BAPNE method. In Á. Martos Martínez, A. B. Barragán Martín, M. d. C. Pérez Fuentes, M. d. M. Molero Jurado, M. d. M. Simón Márquez & M. Sisto (Comps.), *Acercamiento Multidisciplinar Para la Investigación e Intervención en Contextos Educativos* (pp. 475-483). Dykinson, S.L.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J., Arnau-Mollá, A. F., Di Russo, S., Salerno, G., Liendo Cárdenas, A., Asurmendi Telleria, E. & González de Benatuil, M. L. M. (2022d). Bola cantabile: Creative strategies for the classroom from the BAPNE method. In Á. Martos Martínez, A. B. Barragán Martín, M. d. C. Pérez Fuentes, M. d. M. Molero Jurado, M. d. M. Simón Márquez & M. Sisto (Comps.), *Acercamiento Multidisciplinar Para la Investigación e Intervención en Contextos Educativos* (pp. 485-494). Dykinson, S.L.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2022a). BAPNE Fit: Neuromotricity and body percussion in physical activity and sport sciences. *The Educational Review, USA*, 6(2), 37-44. <http://doi.org/10.26855/er.2022.02.001>
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J., & González de Benatuil, L. M. (2022a). Body percussion and urban rhythms as an interdisciplinary resource. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 150, 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/202215001005>
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2022b). Visuomotor skills and neuromotricity in the BAPNE method. Real-Time signaling as a learning resource. In M. A. de la Ossa Martínez (ed.). *La educación y formación musical en el siglo XXI. ¿Somos competentes para el enfoque competencial?* (pp. 303-325). Silex Ediciones.
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J., & González de Benatuil, L. M. (2022b). Practice of BAPNE FIT to Improve Cardiorespiratory Fitness. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 150,

- 1-8.
<https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/202215001006>
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J., Sayago-Martínez, R., Jiménez-Molina, J. B., & Arnau-Mollá, A. F. (2023). Estudio piloto de la evaluación de la ansiedad y la atención a través de la percusión corporal y neuromotricidad en alumnado de secundaria en las clases de Educación Física, Música y Artes plásticas [Pilot study of the assessment of anxiety and attention through body percussion and neuromotricity in secondary school students in Physical Education, Music and Visual Arts classes]. *Retos*, 47, 573–588.
<https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v47.95595>
- Romero Naranjo, F. J., & Andreu Cabrera, E. (2023a). Neuromotricidad como recurso interdisciplinar. Justificación teórico-práctica a través del método BAPNE (Neuromotricity as an interdisciplinary resource. Theoretical-practical justification through the BAPNE method). *Retos*, 49, 350–364.
<https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v49.98903>
- Romero-Naranjo, F. J., & Andreu-Cabrera, E. (2023b). Neuromotricity as a new paradigm. *Journal of Human Sport & Exercise*, 18(1).
- Romero Naranjo, F. J., & Andreu Cabrera, E. (2023c). Condición física y Neuromotricidad. Justificación teórico-práctica según el método BAPNE (Physical condition and neuromotricity. Theoretical-practical justification according to the BAPNE method). *Retos*, 50, 215–227.
<https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v50.98712>
- Romero-Ramos, N., Romero-Ramos, O., & González Suárez, A. J. (2021). Actividad física y funciones cognitivas en personas mayores: Revisión sistemática de los últimos 5 años [Physical activity and cognitive functions in older people: A systematic review of the last 5 years]. *Retos*, 39, 1017-1023.
<https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v0i39.79960>
- Ruthruff, E., Pashler, H. E., & Klaassen, A. (2001). Processing bottlenecks in dual-task performance: structural limitation or strategic postponement?. *Psychonomic bulletin & review*, 8(1), 73-80.
- Salovey, P., & Mayer, J. D. (1990). Emotional intelligence. *Imagination, cognition and personality*, 9(3), 185-211.
- Salter, D. W., Evans, N. J., & Forney, D. S. (2006). A longitudinal study of learning style preferences on the Myers-Briggs type indicator and learning style inventory. *Journal of college student development*, 47(2), 173-184.
- Sasaki, A. C., Pinto, E. B., Mendel, T., Sá, K. N., Oliveira-Filho, J., & D'Oliveira Jr, A. (2015). Association between dual-task performance and balance during gait in community-dwelling elderly people after stroke. *Healthy Aging Research*, 4, 1-7.
- Sheridan, P. L., & Hausdorff, J. M. (2007). The role of higher-level cognitive function in gait: executive dysfunction contributes to fall risk in Alzheimer's disease. *Dementia and geriatric cognitive disorders*, 24(2), 125-137.
- Sohlberg, M. M., & Mateer, C. A. (1987). Effectiveness of an attention-training program. *Journal of clinical and experimental neuropsychology*, 9(2), 117-130.
- Shim, S., Yu, J., Jung, J., Kang, H., & Cho, K. (2016). Effects of motor dual task training on spatio-temporal gait parameters of post-stroke patients. *Journal of Physical Therapy Science*, 24(9), 845-848.
<https://doi.org/10.1589/jpts.24.845>
- Sohlberg, M. M., & Mateer, C. A. (1989). *Introduction to cognitive rehabilitation: Theory and practice*. Guilford Press.
- Terry, M. (2002). Translating learning style theory into developmental education practice: An article based on Gregorc's cognitive learning styles. *Journal of College Reading and Learning*, 32(2), 154-176.
- Tirapu-Ustarroz, J., & Luna-Lario, P. (2008). Neuropsicología de las funciones ejecutivas. *Manual de neuropsicología*, 2, 219-59.
- Torró-Biosca, R., Aparici-Mínguez, F., Arnau-Mollá, A. F., Ulate-Orozco, R. M., Cabrera-Quirós, D. A., & Romero-Naranjo, F. J. (2019). Pilot study into the executive functions of children aged 8-9 BAPNE method. *The European Proceedings of Social & Behavioural Sciences EpSBS*, 60, Article 94.
<https://doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2019.04.02.94>
- Villa de Gregorio, M., Ruiz Pérez, L. M., & Barriopedro Moro, M. I. (2019). Análisis de las relaciones entre la baja competencia motriz y los problemas de atención e hiperactividad en la edad escolar [Analysis of the relationships between low motor competence and attention and hyperactivity problems in school age]. *Retos*, 36, 625-632.
<https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v36i36.68502>
- Wang, S., & Gathercole, S. E. (2013). Working memory deficits in children with reading difficulties: memory span and dual task coordination. *Journal of experimental child psychology*, 115(1), 188–197.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2012.11.015>
- Wu, P. L., Lee, M., & Huang, T. T. (2017). Effectiveness of physical activity on patients with depression and Parkinson's disease: A systematic review. *PLoS one*, 12(7), e0181515.
- Yogev-Seligmann, G., Hausdorff, J. M., & Giladi, N. (2008). The role of executive function and attention in gait. *Movement disorders: official journal of the Movement Disorder Society*, 23(3), 329-342.
- Zambrano-Pintado, R. N., Moncayo Cueva, H. L., López Arcos, S. N., & Bonilla Jurado, D. (2022). Estimulación temprana como programa neurológico en las capacidades y destrezas en niños en etapa infantil [Early stimulation as a neurological programme in the capacities and skills of infants and toddlers]. *Retos*, 44, 252-263.
<https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v44i0.88830>

